

Design and analysis of micro horizontal axis wind turbine using MATLAB and QBlade

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Abstract

The objective of the present work is to design a 300W micro horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) using BEM theory. The design procedure is codified in MATLAB to simplify the routines. SG6040 and SG6041 airfoils are chosen as the hub and tip airfoils respectively while intermediate airfoils are interpolated between hub and tip airfoils. The design parameters like tip speed ratio, wind speed, and power produced are considered for the design. The average wind speed is assumed to be 5m/s based on the local wind speed data collected for a certain period of time. BEM procedure codified in MATLAB software is used to obtain the preliminary blade design parameters such as optimum drag and lift coefficients at various angles of attack, chord, twist, axial induction factor (a) and angular induction factor (a'). The QBlade analysis of 3m diameter wind turbine is carried out at a wind speed of 5 m/s. The results of the analysis show a maximum annual energy production (AEP) of 538kWh and a maximum torque of 15 Nm. This procedure could be effectively adopted for the design and analysis of HAWTs operating at higher wind speeds.

Keywords: Micro wind turbine, MATLAB design, BEM theory, QBlade design, Airfoil, aerodynamic study.

Nomenclature

c	airfoil chord length
k	index of blade element close to the hub
a	axial induction factor
a'	angular induction factor
u	characteristic velocity
P	power
B	number of blades
N	number of blade elements
D	wind turbine rotor diameter
R	rotor radius
d	hub diameter
r	effective rotor length $((D-d)/2)$
F_T	tangential force
F_N	Normal force
C_T	Thrust coefficient
Re	Reynolds number $(\rho V_\infty D/\mu)$ (dimensionless)
C_l	Two – dimensional lift coefficient

$C_{l,0}$	<i>lift coefficient at zero angle of attack¹</i>
C_L	<i>coefficient of lift (dimensionless)</i>
C_{Lmax}	<i>maximum value of the coefficient of lift at stalling angle (α_{stall}) (dimensionless)</i>
C_D	<i>2-dimensional drag coefficient (dimensionless)</i>
C_P	<i>pressure coefficient</i>
r_h	<i>rotor radius at the hub</i>
r_i	<i>radius at a midpoint of a blade section</i>
α	<i>Angle of attack</i>
λ	<i>tip speed ratio</i>
λ_h	<i>local speed ratio at the hub</i>
λ_r	<i>local speed ratio</i>
ρ	<i>density of air (kg/m^3)</i>
μ	<i>viscosity ($\text{kg}/(\text{ms})$)</i>
η	<i>efficiency</i>
Ω	<i>angular velocity of the wind turbine rotor</i>
φ	<i>angle of relative wind</i>
θ_p	<i>section pitch angle</i>
$\theta_{p,0}$	<i>blade pitch angle at the tip</i>
θ_T	<i>blade twist angle</i>
σ	<i>rotor solidity</i>
σ'	<i>local rotor solidity</i>

1. Introduction

Simple structure, compact design, low cost, portable, and low noise have made micro wind turbines a choice of many. The miniature size makes it easier to install and need fewer transportation efforts. Its compact size and versatility make micro wind turbines, a reliable source of energy of the future. Among many approaches to the to the design of HAWT, BEM based design methods are the most efficient and reliable in order to optimize the chord and twist distribution [1]. The large-scale implementation of wind turbine projects as well as, awareness among the public about the utility and handiness of the small rooftop wind turbines have made it all the more necessary to have simple and easily understandable procedure to design a small wind turbine for domestic applications. The objective of this work is to develop a simple procedure to design a micro HAWT for low power applications. In this study, wind turbine design procedure laid down by BEM theory has been coded in MATLAB software whereas, QBlade software is used to analyze the performance of micro wind turbine.

Many researchers have tried to design small wind turbines using different approaches. The design and optimization of the 400W small wind turbine were carried out in order to study the interdependency between solidity (σ), tip speed ratio (λ), pitch angle (θ_p), and maximum power coefficient ($C_{P,max}$) [2]. In their studies, SG6043 airfoil was used as a single airfoil for the entire blade and the influence of chord and twist were studied on the blade solidity ranging from 2% to 30%. A new airfoil was designed to use it in a 2-bladed rotor Air-X marine 400 W, for low Re applications. The rotor blades were provided with taper as well as twist, in addition, to pitch in the

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range of 15° to 20° . The results show that the wind turbine yielded a C_P of 0.255 at a wind speed of 6 m/s and at the θ_P of 18° . The study also found the cut-in speed to be 3.24 m/s and 2 bladed rotor developed more power than 3 bladed one [3]. Field results of a two-meter diameter HAWT were compared with the results generated by a quasi-steady blade element analysis. A large number of trials were conducted on an actual turbine to find the rotor performance parameters and when compared with the theoretical data, it was found that, there are limitations in the traditional theoretical methods of providing the starting of wind turbine with a single cut-in speed. The concepts related to the thrust generation in the blade and its utility in the wind turbine starting and power generation as explained by the BEM theory calculations were also discussed as a part of the investigation [4]. A new family of airfoil was designed to be used in small HAWTs. The researchers found the properties of the airfoil using XFOIL software for low Re. They also conducted wind tunnel tests for the newly designed airfoil and found that, the newly designed airfoil has superior aerodynamic properties and could be used in small HAWT[5]. Researchers estimated the cost-effectiveness of the small HAWTs by comparing three small wind turbines. The return on investment was calculated by considering the investment made on the turbine and performance comparison of three turbines. The comparative study showed that the high cost of the turbines is the main hurdle in mass-scale utilization of small wind turbines than its aerodynamic complexities [6]. Theoretical and experimental investigation to compare the performance of a 2.2 m diameter HAWT working at low Re was tried through BEM method. The aim of the comparison was also to study the applicability of the BEM in modeling the rotor performance of small HAWTs. The results generated from the boundary layer wind tunnel two tests at University of Western Ontario for a wide range of wind speeds and its comparison with the data generated from BEM theory shows an agreeable comparison of results for larger wind turbines while not so accurate for small wind turbines[7]. A computational framework for the optimum design of a small HAWT was initiated using BEM theory. The aim of the study was to smoothen the starting torque of the small HAWT and hence to reduce the starting vibrations in the system. The study suggests that the researchers were successful in obtaining the smooth starting torque for the small HAWT. They used MATLAB for the design purpose and the modeling is done in Pro/ENGINEER while the simulation is carried out in ADAMS software [8]. The cost involved in the innovations in the design of the HAWT blade is meager compared to the savings the optimally designed blade brings with it. Researchers suggest the usage of numerical modeling and computational techniques in the design of the blades before using advanced composite materials to manufacture the blades. Researchers suggest that the aim of the design process is to obtain the highest power from a blade and the only way is to change the shape of the blade without compromising the dynamic and mechanical properties. The main aim of their investigation is to propose a computer program package which would provide optimum solution while considering a number of parameters[9]. Based on the above literature survey it is evident that there is a need for the simple procedure to design a micro HAWT for domestic applications. This kind of simple design procedure is rarely found in the literature for the design and analysis of low Re application of micro HAWT made of SG family airfoils.

2. Aerodynamic design

2.1 Wind Turbine Rotor Design Procedure

Wind turbine rotor design procedure is based on the BEM model originally proposed by Glauert [10]. This procedure combines the blade element theory and momentum theory, which is famously

known as blade element momentum (BEM) theory or simply strip theory. When the blade rotates, each strip produces an annular area and each annular area separates two blades with no connection between them. One-dimensional linear momentum conservation principle is then applied to each of the annular areas in order to analyze the forces and moments developed during the rotation. Finally, the forces and powers developed at each annular section are integrated by including the sectional C_L and C_D , C and θ_T information of the blade[11].

Wind turbine blade design involves many variables such as N , R , C_L , C_D , c , θ_p , θ_T , and α at each section of the blade. Based on wind speed of the place and maximum power (P_{max}) needed, diameter (D) of the rotor is determined. While calculating P , the influence of the C_p and generator and transmission efficiencies (η) are included. Hence, the radius (R) of the rotor is determined from equation (1).

$$P = C_p \eta \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \rho \pi R^2 U^3 \quad (1)$$

To calculate P , the maximum possible C_p needs to be determined, whereas, C_p depends on λ which is the ratio of tip speed of the blade ($R\Omega$), to u i.e. $\lambda = R\Omega/U$. The value of λ depends on the type of application. For water pumping applications, i.e. for low rotor speeds, $1 < \lambda < 3$, whereas, for higher rotor speed applications, $4 < \lambda < 10$ is used. Hence the maximum possible coefficient of power, $C_{p,max}$, and corresponding λ_{opt} are evaluated as per the procedure mentioned in reference[1]. The value of λ corresponding to maximum C_p for a 3 bladed turbine is selected as $C_{p,max}$.

The next step of the design procedure is the selection of airfoil which suites the application. An airfoil is selected based on the size of the rotor as well as the type of application. Normally, for a horizontal axis wind turbine, airfoils with high lift coefficient and a very low drag coefficient are chosen to create good lift conditions at moderate wind speeds.

The entire range of airfoils was analyzed in QBlade software for various α and u and the optimum values of C_L , C_D , and L/D were recorded. Then the blade is divided into ten ($N = 10$) elements and shape of i^{th} element with radius r_i is determined by employing Eq. (2) to Eq. (6) in MATLAB routine.

$$\lambda_{r,i} = \lambda (r_i/R) \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_i = (2/3) \tan^{-1}(1/\lambda_{r,i}) \quad (3)$$

$$c_i = \frac{8\pi r_i}{BC_{L,design,i}} (1 - \cos \phi_i) \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_{T,i} = \theta_{p,i} - \theta_{p,o} \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_i = \theta_{p,i} + \alpha_{design,i} \quad (6)$$

The theoretical dimensions obtained through BEM procedure are modified and adjusted such as linearization of the c , θ_T , and blade thickness to facilitate economic, structural, and manufacturing requirements.

The rotor performance has to be evaluated before finalizing the actual blade dimensions. The iterative procedure employing Eq. (7) to Eq. (9) is used to arrive at induction factors to be used in the determination of the performance parameters.

$$\phi_{i,1} = (2/3) \tan^{-1}(1/\lambda_{r,i}) \quad (7)$$

$$a_{i,1} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{4 \sin^2(\phi_{i,1})}{[\sigma'_{i,design} C_{L,design} \cos \phi_{i,1}]}} \quad (8)$$

$$a'_{i,1} = \frac{1 - 3a_{i,1}}{(4a_{i,1}) - 1} \quad (9)$$

Once the initial induction factors, $(a_{i,1}$ and $a'_{i,1})$ are assumed suitably, the iterative process is started for the j^{th} iteration. For the first iteration, j is considered as one and the angle of the relative wind (φ) and tip loss factor (F) are calculated using Eq. (10) and Eq. (11):

$$\tan \varphi_{i,j} = \frac{U(1-a_{i,j})}{\Omega r(1+a'_{i,j})} = \frac{(1-a_{i,j})}{(1+a'_{i,j})\lambda_{r,i}} \quad (10)$$

$$F_{i,j} = \left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right) \cos^{-1} \left[\exp \left(- \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{B}{2}\right) \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_i}{R}\right)\right]}{\left(\frac{r_i}{R}\right) \sin \varphi_{i,j}} \right\} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

The lift and drag values for i and j^{th} iteration i.e. $C_{l,i,j}$ and $C_{d,i,j}$ are determined using Eq. (12).

$$\alpha_{i,j} = \varphi_{i,j} - \theta_{p,i} \quad (12)$$

Once the induction factors and drag values are found, the local thrust coefficient is calculated using Eq. (13).

$$C_{T_{r,i,j}} = \frac{\sigma'(1-a_{i,j})^2 C_{l,i,j} \cos \varphi_{i,j} + C_{d,i,j} \sin \varphi_{i,j}}{\sin^2 \varphi_{i,j}} \quad (13)$$

The iteration process compares the newly generated values of a and a' and continues till the time $C_{T_{r,i,j}} < 0.96$ as shown in Eq. (14) to Eq. (16).

$$a_{i,j+1} = \frac{1}{\left[1 + \frac{4F_{i,j} \sin^2(\varphi_{i,j})}{\sigma'_i C_{l,i,j} \cos \varphi_{i,j}}\right]} \quad (14)$$

If $C_{T_{r,i,j}} > 0.96$:

$$a_{i,j} = \left(\frac{1}{F_{i,j}}\right) \left[0.143 + \sqrt{0.0203 - 0.6427(0.889 - C_{T_{r,i,j}})}\right] \quad (15)$$

$$a'_{i,j+1} = \frac{1}{\frac{4F_{i,j} \cos \varphi_{i,j}}{\sigma'_i C_{l,i,j-1}}} \quad (16)$$

If the newly calculated induction factors are found within permissible limits, then the other performance parameters are calculated, otherwise, the procedure repeats from Eq. (10) with $j = j+1$.

The power coefficient of the blade as shown in Eq. (17) is the sum integral of the equation of performance at each element and is found in the reference [1].

$$C_P = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{8\Delta\lambda_r}{\lambda^2}\right) F_i \sin^2 \varphi_i (\cos \varphi_i - \lambda_{r,i} \sin \varphi_i) (\sin \varphi_i + \lambda_{r,i} \cos \varphi_i) \left[1 - \left(\frac{C_d}{C_l}\right) \cot \varphi_i\right] \lambda_{r,i}^2 \quad (17)$$

As the blade is divided into N parts, Eq. (18) provides the tip speed ratio at every radial position and C_P at such positions is calculated using Eq. (19).

$$\Delta\lambda_r = \lambda_{r,i} - \lambda_{r,(i-1)} = \lambda/N \quad (18)$$

$$C_P = \frac{8}{\lambda N} \sum_{i=k}^N F_i \sin^2 \varphi_i (\cos \varphi_i - \lambda_{r,i} \sin \varphi_i) (\sin \varphi_i + \lambda_{r,i} \cos \varphi_i) \left[1 - \left(\frac{C_d}{C_l}\right) \cot \varphi_i\right] \lambda_{r,i}^2 \quad (19)$$

Where k is the index of the initial blade section with actual blade airfoil.

2.2 Rotor specifications

The wind turbine performance is predominantly influenced by tip speed ratio (λ) and number of blades (B). Since, number of blades affect the solidity ratio (σ) of the rotor, a careful selection of the number of blades is worth analyzing. Higher is the number of blades, higher is the construction cost of the turbine. Hence, an optimum choice is made between the cost and the solidity ratio. For most of the commercial as well as domestic wind turbines, three blades are considered to be optimum which provide enough starting torque for the wind turbine to start. The rotor specifications used in the present analysis are listed in Table 1.

2.3 MATLAB design procedure

For the present work, MATLAB code written by [12] is used with sufficient modifications to suite the requirements. The MATLAB code consists of four section viz. (i) *statistics diagram*, (ii) *design*, (iii) *off-design* and (iv) *pitching*. The first part of the code i.e. *statistics diagram* is used to determine D , λ , and C_P of the turbine as the output for every input of design wind speed and power. The availability of the free stream velocity, $u = 5\text{m/s}$, $B = 3$, and $P = 300\text{W}$ are provided as the inputs to the code. Based on the inputs, the code gives the $C_{P, max}$, λ , and D as the outputs to be used in the next step.

Chord and twist distribution of the blade are determined using script *design.m*. Once the blade parameters such as chord length (c), twist, and radial distribution of airfoils are obtained, a virtual blade is designed in QBlade software to determine the performance parameters for various inputs.

Table 1. Rotor Specifications

Rotor Diameter (D)	= 3m
Hub (d)	= 0.225m
Effective rotor radius (R)	= 1.3875m
Twist angle, ($\theta = 27.38^\circ - 5.91^\circ$)	= 21.47°
Hub airfoil	SG6040
Tip airfoil	SG6041
Design freestream wind speed (U)	= 5 m/s
Design rotational speed (Ωr)	= 220rpm
Tip speed ratio (λ)	= 7

3. Results and discussion

QBlade is a versatile software available free of cost for every wind turbine researcher. Easy to use and flexibility to edit the design variables have made QBlade a favorite software for young researchers. QBlade has validated the generated data with the wind tunnel data from world renowned universities. The authenticity of QBlade is also due to the large number of research articles getting published in top journals.

Figure 1. Blade chord distribution

Figure 2. Blade twist distribution

In the present work, design parameters obtained from BEM analysis are used to create a wind turbine model in QBlade environment.

QBlade has a flexibility of analyzing the wind turbine for specific values of wind speed and Re as well as for a range of wind speed and Re . Once the analysis is done, the output files are exported to excel to extract required data. The results of the analysis carried out in the present work is presented below.

As shown in Fig. 1, the maximum chord distribution is obtained for 10 - 15% of the blade length from the hub. Though, the bottom section of the blade doesn't produce much power compared to the mid and top section of the blade, it produces necessary torque required for the starting of the turbine. Hence the chord length can be modified to some extent in order to reduce the material cost.

Figure 3. Design angle of attack

Figure 4. Design CL of the blade

Figure 2 shows the plot of θ_T distribution along the blade length. The reason for the twist provided to the turbine blade is to maintain an optimum sectional α with the ensuing air for obtaining the $C_{L, max}$, $C_{D, max}$, and L/D . In Fig. 2 we can clearly see that the twist varies from 27.38° at the hub to 5.91° at the tip.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the α along the blade length. We can see that the α is 9.2° at the hub and goes on reduces to the tip with a value of 4.4° . The α remains consistent if the same airfoil is used for the entire blade otherwise a gradual decrease could be seen in α from hub to tip.

Figure 5. Design L/D ratio along the blade

Figure 6. Re along the blade length

Local lift coefficient distribution along the blade is shown in Fig. 4 and it is seen clearly that the C_L is higher near the hub than the tip due to the gradual reduction of the C of the airfoil.

L/D increases as the radius increases and it reaches a maximum value at around 70% of the length of the blade from the hub as shown in Fig. 5. Higher L/D is essential for the better power generation capabilities of the blade.

Figure 6 shows the Re distribution along the blade length and it is evident from the graph that, as the radius of the blade increases the blade velocity increases and hence the top portion of the blade subtends air at a faster rate than the bottom portion so it results in higher Re .

The blade design process starts with the assumption of a and a' . As the BEM analysis proceeds, the initial guesses are substituted by the newly obtained values for the induction factors and the procedure continues till an optimum solution is obtained as shown in Fig. 7 and Fig 8.

Figure 7. Axial induction factor

Figure 8. Angular induction factor

The normal force (F_N) on the rotor was analyzed for various λ 's and are plotted in Fig. 9. It is quite evident that greater wind speeds bring higher λ which results in higher F_N . For the current study, a value of 7 is assigned to λ as per the plot of Fig. 9 **Error! Reference source not found..**

Figure 9. Normal force developed along the blade length for various TSR

Figure 10. Power developed in the rotor for different wind speeds

The entire design process is aimed to obtain highest power producible at the given wind speed. Figure 10 shows the distribution of power with the variation of wind speed. Though the turbine is designed for a low wind speed of 5 m/s, the turbine is capable of producing more power if subjected to higher wind speeds. Figure 10 also shows that, at 5 m/s the turbine is producing 300 W.

Torque (Q) is the driving force required for the turbine to rotate and the entire design is focused towards generating more torque without sacrificing the structural and vibrational requirements. Figure 11 shows distribution of Q for various wind speeds. For the present study, the rotor is capable of producing 15Nm at 150 rpm.

A turbine's performance is measured in terms of the AEP by the turbine which intern gives a fair economic viability picture of the turbine.

Figure 11. Torque developed at various RPM

Figure 12. Annual energy production (AEP)

Amidst the varying wind speeds, a turbine produces varying power. To get a fair idea about the power generation Weibull parameters are obtained in the form of shape factor (k) and the scale parameter (A) and both represent the characteristic wind speed. Figure 12 shows the AEP distribution against k and it is clear from the graph that, for a Weibull shape value (k) of 2.3 wind turbine produces a maximum of 538 kWh of energy per annum.

4. Conclusion and scope of future work

Present work explains the basic design procedure of a low Re micro HAWT using QBlade and MATLAB software. Low Re airfoils such as SG6040 and SG6041 were considered as a hub and tip airfoils of the blade, whereas, intermediate airfoils were interpolated between the hub and tip airfoils. A HAWT design procedure prescribed by BEM theory was codified using MATLAB software to determine the design properties of the prescribed HAWT blade. The design procedure was repeated many times to establish the reliability of the code and to determine accurate values for the design of a new blade. The design parameters obtained from the MATLAB code were fed to QBlade in order to create a blade. The analysis procedure in QBlade was repeated many times to arrive at the optimized values for performance parameters. After the successful completion of the QBlade trials, the optimum values for power, C_p and AEP were obtained and plotted as mentioned earlier in this paper.

Having said that, the same procedure could also be applied to design small to medium HAWT without any additional changes. The CFD analysis of the rotor could also be carried out to cross-verify the results obtained from the analytical method.

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